

DIFFERENTIATION OF HYPERBOLIC FUNCTION

Abdurahmonova Gulruh Murodullo kizi

Master of Termiz State University

e-mail: abdurahmonovagulruh06@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6410092>

Annotation: In this article discusses about differentiation of hyperbolic function

Keywords: differentiation, properties, circular functions, hyperbolic, ordinary sine

Hyperbolic functions are analogous to trigonometric functions or circular functions in mathematics. The exponential function (e^x) and its inverse exponential functions (e^{-x}), where e is the Euler's constant, are used to create hyperbolic functions in general. We'll go over the fundamental hyperbolic functions, their properties, identities, and examples in detail here.

The circular and trigonometric functions are analogues of the hyperbolic functions. In linear differential equations, distance and angle calculations in hyperbolic geometry, and Laplace's equations in cartesian coordinates, the hyperbolic function appears. In most cases, the hyperbolic function occurs in the real argument known as the hyperbolic angle. The following are the basic hyperbolic functions:

Sine hyperbolic (\sinh)

Cosine hyperbolic (\cosh)

Tangent hyperbolic (\tanh)

From these three basic functions, the other functions such as hyperbolic cosecant (cosech), hyperbolic secant (sech) and hyperbolic cotangent (coth) functions are derived. Let us discuss the basic hyperbolic functions, graphs, properties, and inverse hyperbolic functions in detail.

The basic hyperbolic functions formulas along with its graph functions are given below:

1. Hyperbolic Sine Function

The hyperbolic sine function is a function $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined by $f(x) = [e^x - e^{-x}]/2$ and it is denoted by $\sinh x$

$$\sinh x = [e^x - e^{-x}]/2$$

Graph: $y = \sinh x$ (picture 1)

2. Hyperbolic Cosine Function

The hyperbolic cosine function is a function $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined by $f(x) = [e^x + e^{-x}]/2$ and it is denoted by $\cosh x$

$$\cosh x = [e^x + e^{-x}]/2$$

Graph: $y = \cosh x$ (picture 2)

3. Hyperbolic Tangent Function

The hyperbolic tangent function is a function $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined by $f(x) = [e^x - e^{-x}] / [e^x + e^{-x}]$ and it is denoted by $\tanh x$

$$\tanh x = [e^x - e^{-x}] / [e^x + e^{-x}]$$

Graph: $y = \tanh x$ (picture 3)

Hyperbolic functions, also called hyperbolic trigonometric functions, the hyperbolic sine of z (written $\sinh z$); the hyperbolic cosine of z ($\cosh z$); the hyperbolic tangent of z ($\tanh z$); and the hyperbolic cosecant, secant, and cotangent of z . These functions are most conveniently defined in terms of the [exponential function](#), with $\sinh z = 1/2(e^z - e^{-z})$ and $\cosh z = 1/2(e^z + e^{-z})$ and with the other hyperbolic trigonometric functions defined in a manner [analogous](#) to ordinary [trigonometry](#).

Just as the ordinary sine and cosine functions trace (or parameterize) a circle, so the \sinh and \cosh parameterize a [hyperbola](#)—hence the *hyperbolic* appellation. Hyperbolic functions also satisfy identities analogous to those of the ordinary trigonometric functions and have important physical applications. For example, the hyperbolic cosine function may be used to describe the shape of the curve formed by a high-voltage line suspended

between two towers (see [catenary](#)). Hyperbolic functions may also be used to define a measure of distance in certain kinds of [non-Euclidean geometry](#).

So let's look at how we can easily apply our differentiation formulas for hyperbolic trig functions with a few examples. We know all of our derivative techniques. It's now time to talk about taking the derivatives of hyperbolic functions.

1.	$\frac{d}{dx}[\cosh(5x)] = \sinh(5x) \cdot 5 = 5\sinh x$
2.	$\frac{d}{dx}[\tanh(\sqrt{x})] = \operatorname{sech}^2(\sqrt{x}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}x^{-1/2} = \frac{\operatorname{sech}^2(\sqrt{x})}{2\sqrt{x}}$
3.	$\frac{d}{dx}[\operatorname{csch}(e^{5x})] = -\operatorname{csch}(e^{5x})\operatorname{coth}(e^{5x}) \cdot 5e^{5x} = -5e^{5x} \operatorname{csch}(e^{5x})\operatorname{coth}(e^{5x})$

Hyperbolic Functions Examples

See how easy these rules are!

Inverse Hyperbolic Trig Derivatives

And just as trigonometric functions can be expressed as inverses, hyperbolic trig functions can similarly be defined.

Derivatives of Inverse Hyperbolic Functions

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\sinh^{-1}(f(x))] = \frac{f'(x)}{\sqrt{1+(f(x))^2}}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\cosh^{-1}(f(x))] = \frac{f'(x)}{\sqrt{(f(x))^2 - 1}}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\tanh^{-1}(f(x))] = \frac{f'(x)}{1-(f(x))^2}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\cot^{-1}(f(x))] = \frac{f'(x)}{1-(f(x))^2}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\operatorname{sech}^{-1}(f(x))] = \frac{-f'(x)}{f(x)\sqrt{1-(f(x))^2}}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\operatorname{csch}^{-1}(f(x))] = \frac{-f'(x)}{|f(x)|\sqrt{1+(f(x))^2}}$$

Calcworkshop.com

Inverse Hyperbolic Trig Derivatives

Again, you will notice how strikingly similar the inverse trig and inverse hyperbolic trig derivatives are, just with a slight sign change.

Examples - Inverse Differentiation

So, let's look at a few examples of how we take inverse hyperbolic trig derivatives.

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\sinh^{-1}(9x^2)] = \frac{18x}{\sqrt{1+(9x^2)^2}} = \frac{18x}{\sqrt{1+81x^4}}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\tanh^{-1}(\sqrt{x})] = \frac{\frac{1}{2}x^{-1/2}}{1-(\sqrt{x})^2} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}(1-x)}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\operatorname{sech}^{-1}(\sin x)] = \frac{-\cos x}{\sin x \sqrt{1-(\sin x)^2}} = \frac{-\cos x}{\sin x \sqrt{1-\sin^2 x}} = \frac{-\cos x}{\sin x \sqrt{\cos^2 x}} = \frac{-\cancel{\cos x}}{\sin x \cdot \cancel{\cos x}} = \frac{-1}{\sin x} = -\operatorname{csc} x$$

Pythagorean identity
 $\cos^2 x = 1 - \sin^2 x$

So, all in all, we just have to plug into our formulas and simplify! Together we will use our new differentiation rules for hyperbolic trigonometric functions combined with our other important derivative

formulas and skills for polynomials, exponentials, and logarithmic functions too!

